

Young's Double Slit Mystery

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"Nobody can give you a better explanation of this phenomenon than I have given: that is, a description of it."

Richard Feynman

1 Abstract

"Young's Double Slit Mystery" appears when the double slit experiment was done with single photons, sent one at a time, and giving the same interference pattern as obtained with a laser beam. It is said to be fully explained in Quantum Mechanics with the concept of "superposition" of the wave function of the photon and that there is no other way to explain it. Mathematically it gives the correct answer, but, it doesn't explain the natural process behind.

The principle of "superposition" is based on the idea that a quantum system is in a superposition of many possible states. The mathematical description of the quantum superposition is what is called the "wave function" and is just a probability. For a photon traveling to the double slit, the "superposition" principle means that the photon can be anywhere in the universe [1](Victor Toth). In consequence, with this principle, it is considered that the "wave function" of the photon has an equal probability to be at the two slits at the same time. Then, in the modeling of the double slit, there are two "wave functions" leaving the two slits at the same time. It should be noted that in doing this, there is no need for the existence of a particle!

Accordingly, there is no difference with the resolution of the double slit experiment done by the wave theory of light! But, the wave theory of light is untrue and the resolution using the quantum principle of "superposition" is just mathematics. However, there should be a physical reality behind these two models, wave theory of light and quantum "superposition", which are both supposing that two "waves" are at the two slits at the same time. And also the reality of the existence of the particle in a photon is put into question.

In the following we will propose a physical process to explain the diffraction by a double slit, which needs to have two real waves at the same time at the two slits.

2 History

When in 1801, Thomas Young came up with the idea of the double slit to go against Newton's particle view of light, he couldn't know that he had opened the Pandora's Box. Indeed, the Young's double slit experiment has allowed confirmation that light behaves as a wave and not a particle. But, when Albert Einstein interpreted the Photoelectric Effect, by a light beam composed of quanta of energy, it was stated that the light behaves as a wave and a particle, giving rise to the wave-particle concept. This duality

concept was supposed to be confirmed a few years later by the Compton Effect which consist of the deviation of a photon by a single electron.

Later, Young's double slit experiment was a source of astonishment for all the quantum physicists and in particular to Richard Feynman [2]: he said *'You remember the case of the experiment with the two holes? It's the same thing' I am going to tell you about the experiment with the two holes. It does contain the general mystery; I am avoiding nothing; I am baring nature in her most elegant and difficult form*".

In 1977, for the first time, the emission of single photon was obtained with an attenuated beam of sodium fluorescent atoms containing only one or two atoms which contributed to the fluorescence radiation at any one time [3](Wikipedia). In this way, only single emitters were producing light which, when sent to a double slit, produced the same interference pattern of a light beam, after integration of all the photons. Indeed, it is a "physical" mystery of how single photons, emitted one at a time, can give an interference pattern in a screen behind, as if each photon could go through the two slits at the same time and interfere.

But, this is "physically" impossible with the size of a photon, which is supposed to be of the order of its wavelength in all directions [4](Constantin Meis), which is far smaller than the spacing between the two slits of the experiment (0.5μ compared to 1 mm).

Is there a real physical mechanism for the presence of two waves at the two slits at the same time and which will interfere?

3 What is Light?

A light ray is said to be composed of small energetic entities called "photons" and it is admitted that a photon is a combined particle and a wave. This is the concept of the "wave-particle" duality of a photon, which was accepted after Einstein interpretation of the Photoelectric Effect. To complexify this duality concept, experiments has lead to the idea that particle and wave can't be observed at the same time.

The wave is considered to be an electromagnetic wave with electric and magnetic fields, modelled by Maxwell's equations. This fact often leads to interpret a light ray as a wave encompassing the entire beam, which we will see later is not realistic.

The photon particle is supposed to have a very small size, like an electron at the most. Knowing that the wave length in the visible domain is of the order of a micron or less and that an electron is of the order of 0.0000000001μ , then we can see that the particle, if it is true, is quasi lost in the wave. Moreover, with the "superposition" concept of QED (Quantum Electro Dynamics), it is shown that there is no need of a particle to demonstrate the interference of a double slit, since the "superposition" principle applies only to the wave.

If we go back to the Photoelectric Effect, it has been shown that it can be explained in the same way as Einstein did , without the notion of the presence of a particle [5](Willis E. Lamb, Jr). Oddly, this has never been accepted or discussed.

With the Compton scattering of a photon by an electron it has been claimed also that it is due to the particle behavior of a photon [6](Wikipedia).This conclusion has been challenged in a classical way [25](Jean Loius van Belle). It can be also challenged more simply by the fact that a photon wave has an impulse given by:

$$p = h\lambda \tag{1}$$

With this wave impulse there is no need of a particle to explain Compton scattering. The angle θ of the deviated photon after the scattering by an electron is given by the famous Compton formula and can be rewritten as follows:

$$\cos\theta = 1 - \frac{m_e c}{p}(\lambda\lambda' - \lambda^2) \tag{2}$$

With $m_e c$ the electron impulse, λ' the new wavelength after the impulse, p the wave impulse.

It can be argued that this formula is for high energy photons. But at low energy, like for visible photons, it has been shown that the formula above is modified and contains only the frequency change and the electromagnetic fine structure constant [7](Rouven Essig et al) [8](Wikipedia):

$$\alpha = \frac{e^2}{4\pi\epsilon_0\hbar c} \quad (3)$$

The last parameter means clearly that Compton scattering is an electromagnetic interaction only. This interaction leads to a deviation of the photon from its straight line trajectory. Then, in the following we will consider photons in a light beam as being only a wave, with an impulse like a particle and which properties that has to be conformed. Some aspects of a light beam has never been exposed, which are in particular the spatial and temporal proximity between photons in the beam and the duration of the pulse wave.

4 What is a Photon?

In this chapter we are demonstrating the arguments which will be used for the interpretations of the diffraction by a single slit and by a double slit. The reader may skip to the conclusion of this chapter and go back afterward.

The number of photons emitted by a laser source of 50 mW is of the order of 10^{17} photon/s . If the section of the beam is 100 mm^2 ($\sim 1,1\text{ cm}$ in diameter), and if we suppose the volume of a photon is equal to λ^3 , then for a wave length of 1μ , photons are separated by 66λ in all directions. With these hypothesis, this calculation shows that photons are totally independent in a laser beam.

This behavior is confirmed by comparing the results of double slit experiments done with a laser source and with a single photon source. When both experiments gives the same interference pattern out of the double slit, this means that photons coming out of a laser beam are all independent from each other in the light ray. Then, we can use results done with a laser source with a good certitude that photons are probably not interfering between each other.

In consequence, the double slit experiment has to be interpreted knowing that each photons are individually creating the interference pattern by summing all the contributions. Then when a photon arrives at the double slit how do we explain it being at the two slits at the same time?

The independence of photons of a visible light ray permits also to interpret the interference obtained with a thin film.

A thin film interference can be seen on soap bubbles exposed to sunlight for example. It is explained by the interference of light reflected from the top and the bottom of the film [9](H. H. Roseberry et al). It can be observed also between two glass slides which are touching at one extremity and inclined such that there is a film of air between the two slides. In this case of the two slides the inclination is varying along the distance to the touch point and then can be very large. Lastly it is observed in a Fabry Perot interferometer where the interdistance can be very large compared to the wave length.

Then, how can we interpret interference in a Fabry Perot device if we suppose that the photons are independent in space and time from each others?

The mathematical model of a Fabry Perot interferometer shows that the multiple contributions going out of the device are all issued from an initial wave light [10]: "For the mathematical treatment we can interpret the divergent beam at the entrance of the plates as a superposition of an infinite number of parallel beams with individual angles of incidence, φ , and amplitudes $E_0(\varphi)$ ". This is modeled by the sum of these amplitudes as the geometrical series:

$$E(\varphi) = E_0(\varphi) * T * e^{i2\pi\sigma n \frac{a}{\cos\varphi}} (1 + Re^{-i(2\alpha_R + 2\pi\sigma\delta)} + (Re^{-i(2\alpha_R + 2\pi\sigma\delta)})^2 + \dots) \quad (4)$$

With $E_0(\varphi)$ the initial wave, T and R respectively the transmission and reflection coefficients, α_R the phase shift at the reflection, δ the optical path phase difference, $\sigma = \frac{1}{\lambda}$.

This formula clearly shows that the initial wave entering the Fabry Perot goes out in a multiple fraction of the initial wave, each secondary wave having an optical phase shift due to the reflections and is supposing that the initial photons are all independent. Then all the secondary wave from the initial wave will add together and interfere.

To confirm the preceding, the way quantum mechanics is modeling a Fabry Perot interferometer is to consider a single photon representation in a single coherent Fock state [11](Christoph F. Wildfeuer et al). Let Wikipedia explain what a Fock state is [12]:

“The Fock space is an algebraic construction used in quantum mechanics to construct the quantum states space of a variable or unknown number of identical particles from a single particle Hilbert space H”. This confirms that all the photons in a laser beam are considered to be independent.

The only way to explain the preceding behavior is to consider that the wave has an extension along the propagation path which is far greater than its wavelength and that it can split in multiple secondary waves. Let’s suppose the length of the wave is 10 mm long (10 000 pulse of 1μ wavelength) and redo the above calculation to see how far the wave are apart from each other. If we suppose the extension in the transverse direction is equal to the wave length, the separation between photons is 30 mm, still higher. The reality of the photon wave could be like a series of 10 000 pulses of 1 micron in wavelength for example, or much more! This is the way to explain Fabry Perot interference pattern! The duration in time of such a long pulsation in this case is 30 picosecond ($3 \cdot 10^{-11} s$), sufficiently short to not have been detected yet. What is strange with the Fabry Perot experiment is how the total energy of a single photon gets back after so much divisions?

This is exactly what was exposed on Quora by Bill Otto who is considering that the pulse could be as long as 1m! He said “ what would happen if you had a photon the size of a golf ball? [13]. He said: “We know quite well that photons are in the neighborhood of a meter long because it takes that long for a photon to be emitted, and during that time collisions can occur, causing changes to the photon’s frequency as measured in the laboratory frame of reference. And we know that a thin film a few microns thick will alter how a photon reflects. In fact we know that an etalon a few millimeters thick will cause a photon to reflect differently depending on exactly how thick it is. So a photon interferes with itself demonstrating that it has to be at least a few millimeters long. In fact we can set up a Fabry-Perot interferometer and have photons interfere with themselves in a cavity a meter long. And with a double slit experiment, we can see that photons behave as if they are at least a few centimeters wide for visible light. Then it is very probable that a photon is composed with multiple pulse at the frequency of the light”. No comments.

A photon is also an electromagnetic wave and as such it is often described by its electric field:

$$E(x, y, z, t) = E_0 u(x, y, z, t) e^{i(\omega_0 t - k_0 z)} \quad (5)$$

With E_0 the electric field amplitude, u the description of the envelope of the laser beam, ω_0 the light frequency, k_0 the wave number $(2\pi)/\lambda_0$. But, since photons in a laser beam are all independent, the transversal extension of the single photon electric field has to be known, if we want to analyze a possible interaction with matter atoms.

The transversal extension of a single photon electric field has never really been examined. However, when a hole in a metallic material is shrunk such that the radius is lesser than the wavelength, then the transmission efficiency is very weak.

This conclusion has been challenged by studies on subwavelength hole [14](Yu-Hui Chen):“However, an experiment has shown that, if a subwavelength aperture in a metal film is surrounded by periodic grooves, the transmitted light can emerge as a beam with a small angular divergence instead of being diffracted to a wide angular range”. In this experiment, with a hole lesser than the impacting wavelength and “surrounded by a series of shallow and narrow grooves” (typically $\lambda/10$), light is manipulated by the

experimental device to permit it to go through the hole. More than that, the experimenters are able to design a figure with the outcoming light. It is called surface wave holography.

This subwavelength experiment shows that the photon electromagnetic fields interact at the border of the hole with the atoms in the vicinity. It is the same as the refraction phenomena which is done by the interactions of the photon EM wave with the atoms of the propagating medium. In this case the speed of the photons is slowed down in function of the index of refraction of the medium. For a metallic hole the index of refraction must be “quasi” infinite, since there is no transmission by a metallic surface, and then the photon should be stopped for a while.

To take as an example, let’s calculate the total delay of a photon wave going through a material of indexes of refraction n and a travelling a distance L . It is given by [15]

$$n_{at}\Delta t = \frac{(n-1)L}{c} \quad (6)$$

with n_{at} the number of atoms encountered and Δt the relaxation time of one atom. For an indexes of refraction of 10 and a distance $L = 100 \mu$, we have a total delay for the photon wave of $0.3 \cdot 10^{-11} s$. The time for a creeping wave to transit to the second slit, if the interslit is $1 mm$ wide, is much less than the duration of the photon pulse given above. Then, we can consider that the photon wave and the wave at the other slit could radiate at quasi the same time.

Lastly, a photon is propagating eternally in a straight line in the propagating medium. It has been proposed that it is due to a force like the inertia force for matter which is keeping matter atoms in a straight line with the same velocity eternally, as long as there is no other force [16](Giorgio Toro). In the case of light it stays in a straight line as long as it doesn’t encounter matter electrons.

As we have seen above, a photon is deviated in what is called Compton scattering when the photon is close to an electron. Since both the electron and the photon has an electric field it is quite obvious that the interaction giving the deviation of the photon is of electromagnetic nature. This interaction modifies the inertia force which is maintaining the photon in a straight line.

We propose that what makes this inertia force, developed in the propagating medium, is the electric field of the photon. We propose that when the electric field is perturbed by the presence of matter electrons at a certain location then the inertia force will be modified and will deviate the photon at this location. The new direction will be function of the amplitude modification and the position of the photon with respect to the electrons. This could be the same phenomenon we see in the refraction phenomenon when light enters a new propagating medium.

We can conclude here:

- Photons in a laser beam are all independent. It explained why the interference pattern is the same when a double slit experiment is done with single photons or with a laser beam,
- Thin film interference and Fabry Perot interferometer shows that the photon wave is a multipulse which can be up to 10 000 pulses leading to a length of the multipulse of $10 mm$ for a 1μ wavelength,
- A photon is an EM wave, with no associated particle, which can interact with matter atoms when passing close to a slit. In this case the photon wave speed will be slowed down a lot,
- A photon goes in a straight line until the photon EM wave is modified by the interaction with electrons provoking a change in the trajectory of the photon by a phenomenon of inertia due to the reaction of the propagating medium to the modified EM wave.

5 Diffraction by a Single Slit

From the diffraction pattern by one slit it can be deduced that when a photon goes through the slit it encounters a deviation of its trajectory, and this deviation is in the perpendicular direction to the slit! This means that if you look at a horizontal slit from sufficiently a large distance you won't see an expanded horizontal line but instead an expanded vertical line [17](Hui Peng).

This is not correctly explained in text books and however it is a key to make a correct interpretation of the diffraction pattern with real photons.

When the photon wave reaches a horizontal slit, close to one of the border of the slit (up or down), the electromagnetic field will interact with the atoms of the metallic material on this borders. The part of the impinging electric field of a photon close to a border will be reduced. The force of inertia being proportional to the intensity of the electric field, it will be lesser on this side than on the other parts. The trajectory of the photon will be deviate vertically upwards for the upper border of the horizontal slit and vertically downward for the lower border. Such effects will leads to a diffraction pattern as a vertical line for an extended slit, as observed experimentally.

This modification of the photon's electromagnetic wave by all the atoms in the vicinity, associated with the phenomenon of inertia, is proposed to be the reason of the deviation of the photon wave when leaving the slit, explaining the diffraction phenomenon. Let see in more details how it works.

For a wave polarized with the electric field perpendicular to the slit aperture it may be inferred that the interaction with the atoms at the slit border will be at its maximum. Taking this case of polarization and looking at the photon going through a slit, the closer the photon wave is to the border, the more this modification will be important on the part of the electromagnetic field close to the border. On the opposite part of the wave, the amplitude of the electromagnetic field will not be modified at all. If we assume that the inertia force is in some way proportional to the electromagnetic field amplitude, it is obvious that the inertia force will be lesser on the side of the wave close to the border than on the opposite side. This explains why the trajectory is deviated perpendicularly to the slit border.

Evidently, the case of other wave polarizations has a consequence. Considering the effect of different polarizations of the electric field wave on the diffraction phenomenon by one slit it has been shown that there is a difference in the spatial localisation of the diffraction pattern on the screen [18](Kanghee Lee et al). It shows in particular that since the atoms on the border of the slit will be affected differently by the electric and magnetic wave, due to the polarisation, the result will be also a difference in the modification of the trajectory after the slit. In consequence, the trajectory may not stay on the perpendicular plane to the slits, but may go slightly above or under.

The effect of inertia, in the plane perpendicular to the slits, will quasi-instantaneously change the trajectory of the photon wave and will move it away from the opening of the slit, the angle depending on the position of the photon with respect to the borders and on the polarisation of the wave. This phenomenon will be equivalent on the other border explaining the expansion of the image of the diffraction pattern observed. In the above interpretation there is no other wave than the incident photon wave going to the slit.

6 Diffraction by a Double Slit Experiment

In the double slit experiment, a photon is supposed to go through in one of the slit only. The other slit being some wavelengths away from it, there must be some mechanism to provoke an interference different from the diffraction by one slit.

The photon wave will create currents on the metal surface that will spread everywhere and also to the other slit. Particularly when the photon is passing close to the border on the side of the other slit. Due to the lesser velocity of the photon wave going through the slit, and the long multipulses of the wave, there will be time for the creeping wave on the metal surface to transit to the second slit. It is known

that an electromagnetic wave traveling on the surface of a metallic surface, when it encounters a slit, will generate a high electrical impedance [19] [20]. In the references above, it is shown that the slit will behave as an amplifier and generate an electromagnetic wave. This new electromagnetic wave will be radiated in the adjacent volume to the screen.

The process described above is a physical explanation for the presence of an electromagnetic wave radiated from the second slit, due to the effect of the photon wave going through the first slit.

How there can be an interference pattern in the double slit experiment?

When a photon goes through one of the slits, it will deviate to a new trajectory according to the above explanations for the phenomenon of diffraction by one slit, the trajectory depending on the position of the photon with respect to a border. After leaving the slit on its new trajectory, it will recover the symmetry of the electromagnetic field and then will continue in a straight line.

With a time delay due to the interslit distance, an electromagnetic wave will be radiated from the other slit. This wave is not a photon wave, but a spherical wave, and is not subjected to the inertia phenomenon. In the EMC community, it is common to treat an electromagnetic wave as a plane wave or a spherical wave, with no associated particle. It is also a fact that the treatment done in quantum mechanics for the double slit problem is done without the presence of a particle.

To interpret correctly the interference pattern of a double slit it is necessary to compare the diffraction image of one slit to the interference pattern of a double slit. It has been experimentally documented that the double slit pattern obtained with a laser beam is the sum of the two single slits diffraction image and superposed with it, deep “valleys” with null values separated by $\frac{\lambda D}{d}$ (with D the distance to the screen, d the interslit distance). This behavior can be explained by the secondary electromagnetic wave coming from the other slit.

When the photon wave going out of the first slit encounters the secondary electromagnetic spherical wave emitted from the second slit, there will be a change in the amplitude of the electromagnetic field of the photon wave. The value of the new electric field will depend on the phase shift due to the geometric position of this photon wave, the delay due to the interslit distance and the slowing down of the photon wave.

When the phase shift is such that the electric field of the photon wave, after summation with the secondary electromagnetic wave, goes to zero, there is no way for the photon wave to continue in a straight line. Then, it will go anywhere, depending on a slight dissimmetry of the electric field. Each time the phase shift almost cancels the photon wave, there will be no photon going to the screen. When there is no zeroing or change of the electric field, the photon wave will continue in its initial direction in a straight line.

Then, the phase shift doesn't provoke an extinction of the photon but instead a deviation of it. The null zone on the screen is not due to an extinction of the photon energy but a non presence of any photon!

The sum of the two waves is a classical calculation and the resultant amplitude in function of the position x on the screen is multiplied by $\text{sinc}^2(\frac{\pi d}{\lambda D} * x)$, which shows that the null values are separated by $\lambda D/d$.

The preceding interpretation is clearly shown in Hui Peng experiment [21]. The figure 1 of this paper shows that when a “blocker” is put after the interference zone to partially interrupt the light rays, the pattern is present on the blocker and on the screen far behind meaning that once the "null zone" is created then it goes away unchanged. This behavior cannot be explained by the classical wave interpretation or the “superposition principle”.

It is often mentioned that when the experimenter wants to know “the which way path” of the photon, that the interference pattern disappears leading to a simple diffraction pattern. This fact is important, since it means that the lead of the interference pattern of a double slit is given by the diffraction at the slit where the photon is passing. Depending on the presence or not of the secondary electromagnetic wave the double slit interference will appear or not. It is probable that the procedure needed to know “the which way path” will destroy the secondary wave due to the creeping wave generated by a photon wave or an electron wave.

How the preceding explanation for single photons could be applied to single electrons or single atoms or single molecules, for which there have been reported the existence of interference pattern, when they are sent one at a time toward a double slit? [22](Andrew Das Arusalmy).

We can extrapolate the description of the double slit phenomenon for a single photon (massless or not) to the other particles mentioned above with the De Broglie-Bohm hypothesis for matter particle. Indeed, in this theory, every particle or particle ensemble having a mass has an associated wave, called a pilot wave, which is supposed to conduct the particle or the ensemble. This pilot wave is undoubtedly of electromagnetic nature since they have electric components inside and then all of the above arguments and demonstrations can be transposed to them.

It could be argued also that an interference pattern has been also observed for neutron particles. Even if they have a neutral electric behavior at large distance, at the interdistance between a neutron and an electron in the slit material, they are actually not neutral since they have electric charge inside [23].

7 Conclusion

Man can manage light to make at its will fantastic representations but the reality is that no one knows what light really is. Even, starting from illustrious physicists like Newton, Einstein, Bohr, etc. it is only explained in terms of mathematics without any physical model. In truth, when facing strange behavior, as often in physics, man is sophisticating his thoughts such that we can think it is true. And we are still in trouble with the real physical phenomenon.

A novelty in this paper is the application of Giorgio Toro's idea about the necessity of the existence of a phenomenon to maintain the trajectory of a photon in a straight line, like it is done for matter particles by the force of inertia. These two phenomena are common facts in nature.

We have supposed in addition, that this inertia force for light can be modified by an interaction between the electromagnetic propagating medium and the asymmetry of the electromagnetic field of the photon. This effect of the asymmetry of the photon electromagnetic field appears when the photon wave is touching the atoms of the border of a slit, which induces a change in the trajectory of the photon.

The presence of an electromagnetic wave at the other slit is a classical effect due to an electromagnetic wave impacting a metallic surface, creating a creeping wave at the surface. When encountering the other slit, this creeping wave creates an electromagnetic wave, which is common knowledge in the EMC community. Also, the slowing down of the velocity of the photon permit to have an interference between the photon wave and the electromagnetic wave created at the other slit by the creeping wave on the metal surface.

The result of the interference between the photon wave and the electromagnetic wave from the other slit is the presence of "null zones" in the double slit interference pattern, due to the absence of photon going to the screen when the phase shift is zeroing or cancelling the electric field of the photon wave.

It can be concluded that the interference pattern of a double slit is given by the diffraction of a photon wave passing in only one of the slits and interfering with an electromagnetic wave created by currents induced in the metallic surface by the photon wave and radiating at the second slit. The zero amplitude on the interference pattern of a double slit is due to the absence of photons as explained above. Once the interference is created, it will continue unperturbed as far as it is possible, as shown experimentally by Hui Peng.

This paper put also in question the reality of a particle in the duality concept of light. This reality of a particle associated with an electromagnetic wave has been proposed by A. Einstein and accepted by the physics community by a Nobel Prize. But this conclusion has been challenged in the recent past by showing the detection of a wave by a photodetector, in the same conditions as the photoelectric experiment. In fact, it is current knowledge that in the radio emission community there has never been mentioned the notion of a particle and when using the "superposition principle", physicists admit there is no need of a particle.

It is important that these ideas about the Young's double slit phenomenon should be tested experimentally. A simple experiment with a double slit could be done to justify the above explanations. In such a double slit experiment, the solution to prove it is to put a mask in front of one of the slits, but not in contact with the diaphragm, without closing it. Then, this modification of the apparatus will allow a photon to go through one of the slits without blocking the creeping wave induced by the photon wave to the other slit. If the interference pattern is still there, while the masking of the other slit prevents the "superposition" of the quantum wave to go through this slit, it will be sufficient to prove the new interpretation and declare that the principle of "superposition" of quantum mechanics is an artifact.

Finally, one can argue that the Lamb effect, the Purcell effect and Compton Scattering of a photon by an electron, are all explained by QED (Quantum ElectroDynamic), giving reason to the superposition principle of quantum mechanics. For the first two phenomena it has been shown that Classical Electrodynamics using Maxwell's equations is explaining these phenomena [24](Mikhail Rybin et al). For Compton Scattering it has also been recently explained classically [25](Jean Louis Van Belle).

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